

COSO ERM AND CYBER RISK MANAGEMENT: BOTH SUPPORT INTERNAL AUDIT QUALITY: EVIDENCE FROM THE JORDANIAN BANKING SECTOR

^{1*}MOHAMMAD HAMDAN, ²SAQER AL-TAHAT, ³TAREQ BANI-KHALID and ⁴GHAITH N. AL-EITAN

^{1,2,3,4}Associate Professor, Department of Accounting, School of Business, Al al-Bayt University, Jordan.
Email: ^{1*}mohd_naser78@aabu.edu.jo, ²dr.altahat@aabu.edu.jo, ³tareq_alkhaldi@aabu.edu.jo, ⁴ghaith.eitan@aabu.edu.jo

Abstract

This study aimed to explore the impact of COSO ERM and Cyber risk management on internal audit quality in the Jordanian banking sector. To achieve that the researcher designed a 45-items questionnaire distributed to 379 respondents (internal auditors). The data was analysed through the SPSS and Smart PLS, to find the impact of COSO ERM and Cyber risk management on internal audit quality. This study found a statistically significant positive impact for the COSO ERM dimensions (Monitoring, Internal Environment, Risk Assessment and Risk Response, Objective Setting and Event Identification, Control activities and Information and communication) on the Internal audit quality. And a statistically significant positive impact for the Cyber risk management dimensions (Cyber risk assessment, Define critical processes and supporting information assets and Create a cyber-risk profile) on Internal audit quality.

Keywords: COSO ERM, Cyber risk management, internal audit quality, Jordanian banking sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

The internal audit is responsible for protecting the organization's assets and the continuity of its performance, the internal audit faces challenges represented by the continuous expansion of the scope of its tasks, and the need to continuously develop its capabilities as well. It also provides a range of assurance and advisory services to the various sections and departments of the organization, which necessitates the importance of possessing the distinguished knowledge and skills that qualify it to carry out its duties to the fullest, and ensure the implementation of the controls as required (Hamdan & Hosban, 2015).

On the other hand, cyber risks are considered as negative activities targeting the infrastructure by exploiting security holes in it, with the aim of affecting the activities of this organization and its capabilities in all its various forms and aspects, or revealing, modifying or destroying its information assets (Hamdan, 2017); (Knudson, 2018), which means that cyber risks occur in a variety of forms and with different objectives, which necessitates the need to find policies, controls and mechanisms to reduce these risks (Johnson, 2015), and find ways to assess and adapt to them.

These policies, controls, mechanisms and methods of evaluation must be developed on an ongoing basis to keep pace with developments that occur in the forms of cyber risks (Renaud,

et al., 2020), which necessitates the need for the organization to invest in cyber security constantly (Mogoane, et al., 2019).

The need to develop the internal audit profession requires following up on developments in both the academic and professional fields, so this study noted that the banking sector is a fertile and attractive environment for exposure to cyber problems, threats and risks, and that it suffers from these risks and their dependencies, according to a study (Hamdan & Hosban, 2015), which concluded that there is a role for the auditor in planning and reducing the risks of the information technology environment in the banking sector, and the study of (Hamdan, 2017), which found that there is a relationship between network security and the documentation of audit evidence policies in light of the mediating variable, the culture of accounting information security, as for the regional level, the study (Ojeka & Egbide, 2017); (Ali, 2019) found that cyber risks negatively affect the banking sector in the economy of the Gulf Cooperation Council countries, and also the study (Berberoğlu and Uzun, 2018) concluded that there is no negative impact of cyber-attacks on the Turkish banking sector although there have been some attacks on this sector.

As for the global level, a study (Ojeka, et al., 2017) concluded that there is an impact of cyber-attacks on Internet banking services. Also, the international study (Islam, et al., 2018), which concluded that the characteristics of the internal audit function have a positive impact on the cybersecurity audit process, and as the study (Chang, et al., 2019) that found an impact of the effectiveness of internal audit factors in managing cybersecurity in banking institutions, and a study (Alina et al., 2017); (Hess, 2021), which found that internal audit has a major role in mitigating cybersecurity risks and responding to them in the following stages: prevention, detection, disposal, and improvement. Finally, the studies by (Lois, et al., 2020); (Al-Moshaigeh, et al., 2019), who concluded that the skills and procedures used by internal auditors and their training have a significant impact against cyber risks. Based on the above, the problem of the study is to reveal the relationship between each of COSO ERM & Cyber risk management in the quality of internal audit in banks.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Internal Audit

It has been found that internal audit represents an independent tool for examination and judgment that follows the authority of management, and works to continuously provide information about the accuracy of internal control systems, the efficiency and performance of operations and tasks and their effectiveness in all departments of the organization (Spira & Michael, 2003), and auditing financial and accounting operations systems and how they work, and methods Presenting the information they provide to clearly reflect the results of these processes (Powell, et al., 1992).

On the other hand, internal audit is an aid affiliated with the bank's management that works to detect and deter fraud and risks that have occurred or are likely to occur, and this is done by carrying out a set of checks and evaluations of the level of performance of the internal

control system and ensuring the adequacy and effectiveness of its operations (Graham, 2015); (Hamdan, 2013). In addition, internal audit was considered a flexible profession that conducts objective assessments and analyzes on the efficiency and effectiveness of tasks in the bank on an ongoing basis and also upon request (Pickett & Jennifer, 2010), to provide the relevant authorities with information and proposals to correct errors and to reduce fraud and non-compliance and optimal use of resources (Powell, et al., 1992).

2.1.1 Internal Audit Quality

In order to achieve efficiency, the internal audit is committed to exerting the highest levels of caution and awareness, exerting the utmost possible and appropriate effort at all stages, whether the stage of preparing the appropriate audit plan, or the stage of evaluating the application of accounting principles and standards, and international internal auditing standards, or the stage of reporting on the results of the internal audit process (Mansor, et al. al., 2018).

To achieve the requirements of the efficiency of the internal audit, the internal audit department must take into account the technical and scientific capabilities of the individuals in charge of the audit process so that they are appropriate to the nature and quality of the tasks under audit. This department must provide programs that enable those conducting the audit process to acquire knowledge and skills that are in line with developments occurring in the scope of this profession. (Drogalas, et al., 2017), It is the responsibility of the Internal Audit Department to carry out the supervisory and oversight tasks on the implementation of the internal audit process to ensure its correct, efficient and effective implementation. The basis for internal auditors to fulfill their obligations and assume the responsibilities entrusted to them is that they hold an appropriate academic qualification (Pickett & Jennifer, 2010), and to maintain the continuity of professional learning, which is represented by a set of experiences, training courses and practical professional certificates related to the audit profession, whether it is in the fields of accounting, statistics, information security, or risk management that develops their abilities and capabilities, which leads to the completion of their tasks efficiently (Spira & Michael, 2003).

The internal audit must also enjoy complete and comprehensive independence in all stages and aspects of the audit process (Mok, et al., 2018), (Li, et al., 2018). The auditor should be unbiased and objective in the performance of his work and when issuing his opinion on the reports he prepares on the subject of the audit process, whether accounting, financial, administrative or operational, in a way that ensures an honest and fair position (Mansor, et al., 2018), (Spira & Michael, 2003), (Mennicken , 2008).

2.2 COSO ERM Framework:

In the year 2004, the COSO ERM Framework was developed to include four objectives by adding a strategy objective, and eight components by adding three components: setting objectives, identifying positive and negative events that may affect the organization's ability to implement the strategy and achieving objectives, and developing response to risk

assessment (COSO, 2004), there is a direct relationship between the goals that the economic unit seeks to achieve, and the components of risk management in them, which represent what is required to achieve these goals (Curkovic, et al., 2018).

H1: There is a significant positive impact of COSO-ERM dimensions in maximization and enhancing of the Internal Audit Quality.

2.2.1 Internal Environment

The philosophy of the risk management environment contains (knowledge of danger, integrity of moral values, ability to comply, management philosophy design, risk appetite, authority and responsibility, internal assessments, human resource management policies), and it can be said that the internal environment is one of the most important components of risk management, where Affects all other elements through the development of strategies and objectives of the organization to identify and assess the risks resulting from its operations, control and organization of control activities and communication systems (Flaherty, et al., 2004).

H1.1: There is a significant positive impact of internal environment in maximization and enhancing of the Internal Audit Quality.

2.2.2 Objective Setting and Event Identification

Objectives must be set before events are identified (Romny, et al., 2012). The main and subsidiary goals are identified at the strategic level that support the vision of business organizations and work to create value for them, so that they help improve the decision-making process, and compliance goals are achieved by following the laws and regulations (COSO, 2004). The objectives must also be consistent with the organization's vision and mission, and must be consistent with the willingness to take risks and the ability to withstand it (Williamson, 2007). The objectives must be characterized by ease, understanding and consistency with the objectives set at the level of the organization, provided that they are integrated with the gradual chain in achieving the sub-goals in the various sub-units, and for each group of them, performance measures and success factors should also be established to determine whether the goals have been achieved, or to identify alternative ways to achieve them for each alternative that is identified, and to assess the risks involved, (Romny, et al., 2012), on the other hand, management must identify potential events that can occur and affect the organization, and determine whether they represent opportunities or whether they may affect the organization's ability to succeed in implementing strategies and achieving goals (Hamdan, et al., 2021), (Frigo & Anderson, 2011).

H1.2: There is a significant positive impact of Objective Setting and Event Identification in maximization and enhancing of the Internal Audit Quality.

2.2.3 Risk Assessment and Risk Response

Risk assessment is the core of the ERM process, in which the organization considers potential events that may affect the achievement of objectives (Frigo & Anderson, 2011). The risks will be evaluated after they have been determined and identified, and the risk assessment

includes measuring the potential size of the loss and the probability of its occurrence, then arranging work priorities, according to the severity of their potential impact (Romny, et al., 2012). It also includes risk assessment (inherent and residual risks), where the management must evaluate events from the perspective of the possibility of occurrence and their impact in the event of occurrence, and this is done through the use of a set of quantitative and qualitative methods, then the positive and negative effects of the potential events will be studied immediately or by category in all the activities of the organization (NTOSAI/PSC, 2007a).

After assessing the risks, management determines how to respond, including avoiding, reducing, sharing, or accepting risks (Liang, et al., 2013). The management evaluates the potential risks and their implications, as well as the costs and benefits that result from them, and the management identifies opportunities that may be available at the organizational level (Hamdan, & Al-Hajri, 2021).

H1.3: There is a significant positive impact of Risk Assessment and Risk Response in maximization and enhancing of the Internal Audit Quality

2.2.4 Control activities

Control activities are the policies and procedures carried out by management to help ensure the implementation and application of risk responses across all levels and functions of the organization (Graham, 2015); (Hamdan, 2013). It includes a variety of activities such as approvals and licenses, verification, settlements and feedback on operational performance, asset protection, and segregation of duties (Hosban & Hamdan, 2015). Risk responses are attacked by the control activities that represent the response to the risks (Bergquist, 2001). After selecting the responses to the risk, management identifies the control activities that represent the response to the risks. After selecting the responses to the risk, management identifies the necessary regulatory activities to help ensure that the risk responses are implemented correctly and in a timely manner. (COSO, 2004).

H1.4: There is a significant positive impact of Control activities in maximization and enhancing of the Internal Audit Quality

2.2.5 Information and communication

Information and communication is the process that links each of the other components with each other, and the relevant information is identified and reported in the form and time frame that enables employees to carry out their responsibilities, and the sources of information may be internal or external on the one hand, and on the other hand, it may be current, historical or projected (Romny, et al., 2012). Risk management in the organization may require the availability of a set of information that is necessary to achieve the objectives of the internal audit (NTOSAI/PSC, 2007a).

In addition, there is a need for information at all levels of the organization to discover, identify and evaluate risks, and respond to them. It is worth noting that information is obtained from internal and external sources and is analyzed in light of the strategy and

objectives determined by the organization's management, taking into account risk analysis, and identifying degree of response.

H1.5: There is a significant positive impact of Information and communication in maximization and enhancing of the Internal Audit Quality

2.2.6 Monitoring

To ensure that the ERM is operating effectively and continuously, monitoring processes must be activated in it, and this is achieved by activating follow-up activities or through a series of separate evaluations covering various aspects of the risk management process (Gjerdrum & Peter, 2011). In addition, the management of the organization at various levels must take responsibility for monitoring ERM, monitoring financial and operational performance as part of their primary duties (Moeller, 2007); (Beasley, et al., 2012).

The risk management in the organization carries out the follow-up process and evaluates its effectiveness by following up on the ongoing activities and conducting separate evaluations for each of them (Yap & Yap 2018). The scope and frequency of separate assessments depends primarily on the assessment of risks and the effectiveness of ongoing monitoring procedures, with the need to report deficiencies.

H1.6: There is a significant positive impact of Monitoring in maximization and enhancing of the Internal Audit Quality

2.3 Cyber security in the banking sector

(Muegge & Craigen, 2015) indicated that cybersecurity is: the process that provides protection for information assets that have been entered, stored, operated and transmitted via the Internet, and this protection is done to reduce cyber risks and work to address their impact on the banking sector. (Camillo, 2017) indicated that cybersecurity is a balanced process to provide an appropriate level of protection that counteracts known or assumed cyber threats, and which enables the banking sector to maintain the continuity of its systems and users to perform their functions, to achieve their business objectives and operational tasks. (Servidio & Ryan, 2015) considered cybersecurity as a computer science that includes techniques, mechanisms and practices that emerge from the concepts, policies and frameworks that govern and regulate cybersecurity, which are used to protect computers, infrastructure, and applications.

2.3.1 Cyber risk management

A cyber risk is a situation or event that can be exploited that intentionally or unintentionally negatively affects one or more security vulnerabilities (Camillo, 2017), which are within the scope of information assets and the banking information and communications technology environment consisting of individuals, processes, data and systems and the networks that are linked and interact with each other (Servidio & Ryan, 2015). He defined it as a harmful accident or incidents that result in disruptions or dysfunctions of the components and aspects of the banking sector's cybersecurity, which has negative effects (Selby, 2017).

On the other hand, it was defined as an opportunity to incur a loss resulting from the exposure of the banking sector, its employees, customers, or the parties it deals with, to the threat of an event or a possible occurrence that exploits its weak capabilities and poor capabilities in achieving cybersecurity requirements (Craig, et al., 2014). And Akinrolabu, et al., (2019) defined the concept of cyber risk as exploiting the absence or weakness of security controls or countermeasures in information assets in the critical IT infrastructure, to steal an asset, corrupt it, delete or damage it that results in an impact Negative results in the loss of the banking sector or the weakening of confidence in it. Whereas (Jibril, 2020) described it as the risks of disruption of the information technology systems of the banking sector or the failure or destruction of its operations, which leads to financial loss, disruption, or damage, which affects the reputation of the banking sector, its financial position or the continuity of its business.

H2: There is a significant positive impact of Cyber risk management in maximization and enhancing the of the Internal Audit Quality.

This one derived into three sub-hypothesis as following:

H2.1: There is a significant positive impact of Define critical processes and supporting information assets in maximization and enhancing the of the Internal Audit Quality.

H2.2: There is a significant positive impact of Cyber risk assessment in maximization and enhancing the of the Internal Audit Quality.

H2.3: There is a significant positive impact of Create a cyber-risk profile in maximization and enhancing the of the Internal Audit Quality.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, the descriptive and analytical approaches were used, where the study variables were described through previous studies, and then measured the variables of the study, and then analyzed statistically to show the impact of COSO ERM and Cyber risk management on Internal audit quality in the Jordanian banking sector Data collection sources

In this study, the method of collecting the study data is presented in two main sources:

- 1) Secondary data sources: these are books, periodicals, journals, and the Internet, where these types of secondary sources of data are referenced in order to build the theoretical background and understand the subject of the study.
- 2) Primary data: Where the researcher collected the data of the preliminary study through the use of questionnaire as a major tool developed specifically to reach the results of the study and address its analytical aspects of the subject of the study.

Population and Sample

The study population is made up of (23) Banks according to the records of the Association of Banks in Jordan (<https://www.abj.org.jo/Default/Ar>) and a representative sample of the study

community was taken consisting of (379) internal auditors and the questionnaire was distributed to them by using google form surveys.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table I presents the summary statistics for each COSO-ERM dimensions, Cyber Risk Management dimensions and the Internal Audit Quality

	Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Degree of Approval	Rank
Table I. Summary statistics	1.internal environment	4.214	0.601	-0.796	1.073	Agree	1
	2.Objective Setting and Event Identification	4.004	0.699	-0.322	-0.352	Agree	5
	3.Risk Assessment and Risk Response	4.093	0.601	-0.348	-0.218	Agree	3
	4.Control activities	3.712	0.809	-0.735	0.717	Agree	10
	5.Information and communication	3.494	0.800	-0.017	-0.333	Neutral	12
	6.Monitoring	4.139	0.637	-0.558	-0.291	Agree	2
	COSO-ERM	3.943	0.517	-0.194	-0.201	Agree	6
	1.Define critical processes and supporting information assets	3.938	0.915	-0.944	0.659	Agree	8
	2.Cyber risk assessment	3.943	0.748	-0.862	1.118	Agree	7
	3.Create a cyber-risk profile	3.653	0.922	-0.666	0.493	Neutral	11
	Cyber risk management	3.845	0.758	-0.771	0.893	Agree	9
	internal audit quality	4.079	0.682	-0.651	0.192	Agree	4

Table I shows that the mean value of all dimensions of COSO-ERM have an agreement degree except of information and communication dimension was neutral the mean values of the COSO-ERM ranges between (3.494 - 4.139) The dimensions were in the following order in terms of the highest application (1. Monitoring, 2. Internal Environment, 3. Risk Assessment and Risk Response, 4. Objective Setting and Event Identification, 5. Control activities and 6. Information and communication) as for the total COSO-ERM dimensions the mean value reach (3.943) with an agreement degree. the next related mean value of all dimensions of Cyber Risk Management have an agreement degree except of Create a Cyber-Risk Profile dimension was neutral the mean values of the Cyber Risk Management ranges between (3.653 - 3.943) The dimensions were in the following order in terms of the highest application (1. Cyber risk assessment, 2. Define critical processes and supporting information assets and 3. Create a cyber-risk profile) as for the total Cyber Risk Management dimensions the mean value reach (3.845) with an agreement degree. Finally, the mean value of Internal Audit Quality has an agreement degree were the mean value reach (4.079).

4.2 Discriminant Validity

Square Root of AVE, suggested by (Fornell & Larcker, 1981) were used to test the discriminant validity (Table II) and as all loadings of an indicator on its assigned latent variable higher than its loading on all other latent variables, the requirement for discriminant validity was fulfilled:

Latent / Indicator	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.internal environment	0.75									
2. Objective Setting and Event Identification	0.55	0.85								
3. Risk Assessment and Risk Response	0.62	0.61	0.71							
4. Control activities	0.43	0.41	0.60	0.81						
5. Information and communication	0.43	0.37	0.44	0.65	0.67					
6. Monitoring	0.52	0.34	0.56	0.60	0.61	0.77				
7. Define critical processes and supporting information assets	0.33	0.22	0.43	0.56	0.54	0.76	0.92			
8. Cyber risk assessment	0.31	0.34	0.44	0.59	0.47	0.57	0.67	0.82		
9. Create a cyber-risk profile	0.44	0.36	0.46	0.66	0.57	0.58	0.64	0.74	0.86	
10. internal audit quality	0.50	0.36	0.51	0.60	0.54	0.65	0.66	0.72	0.77	0.78

as seen in table II all the loading of each indicator on its assigned latent variable is higher than its loading with other variables which means that the degree to which a measure diverges from (i.e., does not correlate with) another measure whose underlying construct is conceptually unrelated to it.

4.3 Cross Loading

If a variable is found to have more than one significant loading it is termed a cross-loading, which makes it troublesome to label all the factors which are sharing the same variable and thus hard to make those factors be distinct and represent separate concepts as shown in table III.

		internal environment	Objective Setting and Event Identification	Risk Assessment and Risk Response	Control activities	Information and communication	Monitoring	Define critical Processes and supporting information assets	Cyber risk assessment	Create a cyber-risk profile	internal audit quality
	Q1	0.754	0.455	0.417	0.324	0.344	0.344	0.223	0.238	0.376	0.383
	Q2	0.811	0.426	0.527	0.392	0.414	0.506	0.379	0.333	0.438	0.350
	Q3	0.687	0.291	0.382	0.237	0.231	0.341	0.258	0.224	0.268	0.305
	Q4	0.661	0.384	0.500	0.300	0.264	0.380	0.175	0.190	0.254	0.275
	Q5	0.818	0.472	0.490	0.332	0.330	0.360	0.195	0.148	0.291	0.314
	Q6	0.517	0.830	0.495	0.392	0.334	0.257	0.148	0.301	0.360	0.317
	Q7	0.425	0.865	0.498	0.271	0.315	0.277	0.192	0.258	0.259	0.235
	Q8	0.441	0.843	0.556	0.365	0.301	0.328	0.226	0.303	0.292	0.355
	Q9	0.522	0.511	0.635	0.318	0.236	0.419	0.282	0.270	0.276	0.352
	Q10	0.505	0.512	0.811	0.442	0.370	0.461	0.328	0.352	0.365	0.351
	Q11	0.475	0.473	0.666	0.449	0.428	0.388	0.380	0.329	0.381	0.341
	Q12	0.326	0.350	0.699	0.290	0.118	0.257	0.187	0.285	0.254	0.298
	Q13	0.380	0.329	0.745	0.349	0.171	0.318	0.221	0.296	0.281	0.343
	Q14	0.402	0.389	0.685	0.613	0.447	0.460	0.373	0.318	0.354	0.469
	Q15	0.401	0.401	0.588	0.849	0.542	0.527	0.482	0.462	0.549	0.499
	Q16	0.355	0.271	0.536	0.805	0.429	0.526	0.438	0.418	0.455	0.454
	Q17	0.374	0.309	0.542	0.779	0.429	0.448	0.383	0.352	0.392	0.435
	Q18	0.301	0.285	0.354	0.809	0.650	0.452	0.483	0.542	0.614	0.513
	Q19	0.288	0.371	0.354	0.784	0.663	0.454	0.453	0.605	0.645	0.508
	Q20	0.320	0.341	0.372	0.714	0.825	0.501	0.510	0.571	0.614	0.517
	Q21	0.270	0.238	0.203	0.375	0.729	0.311	0.293	0.261	0.315	0.318
	Q22	0.121	0.142	0.044	0.120	0.632	0.060	-0.019	-0.033	0.028	-0.044
	Q23	0.349	0.212	0.379	0.329	0.612	0.536	0.397	0.168	0.292	0.376
	Q24	0.498	0.273	0.430	0.471	0.390	0.729	0.463	0.377	0.396	0.489
	Q25	0.410	0.257	0.434	0.401	0.504	0.767	0.487	0.355	0.387	0.511
	Q26	0.368	0.193	0.452	0.360	0.441	0.701	0.447	0.381	0.372	0.446
	Q27	0.377	0.280	0.410	0.538	0.508	0.805	0.703	0.501	0.505	0.501
	Q28	0.343	0.293	0.404	0.510	0.505	0.819	0.788	0.562	0.550	0.544
	Q29	0.371	0.268	0.428	0.549	0.562	0.743	0.921	0.581	0.615	0.632
	Q30	0.244	0.144	0.363	0.476	0.443	0.660	0.922	0.648	0.567	0.587
	Q31	0.190	0.194	0.361	0.368	0.322	0.582	0.696	0.703	0.461	0.511
	Q32	0.176	0.164	0.188	0.156	0.027	0.203	0.173	0.658	0.231	0.222
	Q33	0.215	0.295	0.356	0.542	0.416	0.397	0.500	0.892	0.725	0.601
	Q34	0.321	0.331	0.369	0.554	0.464	0.467	0.519	0.879	0.829	0.673
	Q35	0.339	0.355	0.413	0.534	0.451	0.419	0.518	0.781	0.894	0.638
	Q36	0.379	0.289	0.336	0.602	0.543	0.483	0.533	0.685	0.883	0.626
	Q37	0.424	0.283	0.433	0.560	0.474	0.603	0.586	0.631	0.799	0.746
	Q38	0.396	0.297	0.400	0.479	0.390	0.571	0.608	0.635	0.623	0.781
	Q39	0.404	0.298	0.373	0.472	0.409	0.595	0.633	0.653	0.680	0.844
	Q40	0.392	0.254	0.392	0.500	0.470	0.567	0.533	0.676	0.667	0.801
	Q41	0.345	0.250	0.327	0.549	0.469	0.478	0.500	0.619	0.656	0.746
	Q42	0.351	0.263	0.449	0.449	0.456	0.415	0.464	0.460	0.571	0.742
	Q43	0.389	0.314	0.414	0.483	0.415	0.414	0.393	0.451	0.551	0.746
	Q44	0.422	0.277	0.452	0.395	0.426	0.486	0.470	0.430	0.511	0.779
	Q45	0.394	0.290	0.400	0.348	0.336	0.472	0.445	0.436	0.508	0.748

Table III. Cross-Loading statistics

Table III shows that each variable belongs to their construct and highly correlated with them, which means that there are no problems of cross loadings between variables. Based on (Hair et al., 2010) the criteria to assess loading at cut-offs (>0.50) which means all variables loading to its constructs.

4.4 Convergent Validity

Convergent validity which is the degree to which multiple items to measure the same concepts are in agreement, based on (Hair et al., 2010) the criteria to assess convergent validity are: (1) Cronbach's Alpha at cut-offs (>0.70), (2) Composite reliability at cut-offs (>0.70), (3) Average Variance Extracted (AVE) at cut-offs (>0.50), table IV shows the results of convergent validity:

	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Table IV Convergent Validity statistics	1. internal environment	0.802	0.864	0.696
	2. Objective Setting and Event Identification	0.801	0.883	0.716
	3. Risk Assessment and Risk Response	0.802	0.858	0.690
	4. Control activities	0.864	0.902	0.735
	5. Information and communication	0.852	0.962	0.795
	6. Monitoring	0.822	0.876	0.708
	7. Define critical processes and supporting information assets	0.823	0.919	0.751
	8. Cyber risk assessment	0.897	0.947	0.779
	9. Create a cyber-risk profile	0.822	0.894	0.727
	10. internal audit quality	0.905	0.923	0.755

As seen from table IV all the Cronbach's alpha values are higher than 0.7, all the Composite reliability values are higher than 0.7 and all the AVE values are higher than 0.5, which means that the constructs are valid.

4.5 Assessment of the Structural Model

As shown in Figure I the aim of the structural model is to examine the impact of COSO ERM & Cyber risk management on internal audit quality as follow:

The model shows that the COSO ERM and Cyber risk management can explain 68.1% of the internal audit quality. According to the (Falk & Miller, 1992) the explanatory power of the R2 above 10% is acceptable.

Furthermore, table V shows the Stone–Geisser Q2, R2 and the effect size of f2 as follow:

Table V Q ² , R ² and F ² statistics	Model	Q ²	f ²	R ²
	COSO-ERM	0.399	0.105	0.681
	Cyber risk management		0.609	

According to Cohen's (1988) guidelines $f^2 \geq 0.02$, $f^2 \geq 0.15$, and $f^2 \geq 0.35$ represent small, medium, and large effect sizes, respectively. accordingly, there is a large effect size of each relationship in the study model the highest effect size is for the relationship between the cyber risk management and internal audit quality, where the lowest effect size for the relationship between the COSO-ERM and internal audit quality. Accordingly, CRM have a higher effect size than COSO-ERM which means that CRM have a greater power to effect on internal audit quality than COSO-ERM.

Furthermore, Stone–Geisser Q-square is predictive relevance, measures whether a model has predictive relevance or not (> 0 is good). Further, Q2 establishes the predictive relevance of the endogenous constructs. Q-square values above zero indicate that your values are well reconstructed and that the model has predictive relevance, in this study the Q2 values are higher than zero which means the study model has a predictive relevance.

5.HYPOTHESIS TESTING

in order to test the study hypothesis, the bootstrapping technique were used in the SmartPLS 3.0 Software for the 2nd order model construct, the result of the main hypothesis testing is shown in table VI as follow:

Table VI First Order Effect		Relationship	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values
	H1	COSO-ERM -> internal audit quality	0.258	5.780	0.000
	H2	Cyber risk management -> internal audit quality	0.622	14.995	0.000

According to the results (Table VI), COSO-ERM -> internal audit quality has a ($\beta = 0.258$, $p < 0.01$) which mean there is a significant positive impact of COSO-ERM dimensions in maximization and enhancing of the Internal Audit Quality. The next interesting result is that, Cyber risk management -> internal audit quality ($\beta = 0.622$, $p > 0.01$) which mean there is a significant positive impact of Cyber risk management in maximization and enhancing the of the Internal Audit Quality. Therefore, H1 and H2 are supported.

The result of the 2nd order (alternative) hypothesis testing is shown in table VII as follow:

	Relationship	Path	T	P Values	
		Coefficient	Statistics		
Table VI Second Order Effect	H1.1	internal environment -> internal audit quality	0.056	5.497	0.000
	H1.2	Objective Setting and Event Identification -> internal audit quality	0.035	5.457	0.000
	H1.3	Risk Assessment and Risk Response -> internal audit quality	0.064	5.385	0.000
	H1.4	Control activities -> internal audit quality	0.074	5.438	0.000
	H1.5	Information and communication -> internal audit quality	0.033	5.749	0.000
	H1.6	Monitoring -> internal audit quality	0.068	5.867	0.000
	H2.1	Define critical processes and supporting information assets -> internal audit quality	0.176	14.155	0.000
	H2.2	Cyber risk assessment -> internal audit quality	0.249	12.726	0.000
	H2.3	Create a cyber-risk profile -> internal audit quality	0.263	12.315	0.000

According to the results (Table VII), the alternative hypothesis related to COSO-ERM (internal environment -> internal audit quality, Objective Setting and Event Identification -> internal audit quality, Risk Assessment and Risk Response -> internal audit quality, Control activities -> internal audit quality, Information and communication -> internal audit quality, Monitoring -> internal audit quality) have a ($p > 0.01$). Therefore, H1.1, H1.2, H1.3, H1.4, H1.5 and H1.6 are supported. On the other hand, the alternative hypothesis related to Cyber Risk Management (Define critical processes and supporting information assets -> internal audit quality, Cyber risk assessment -> internal audit quality, Create a cyber-risk profile -> internal audit quality) have a ($p > 0.01$). Therefore, H2.1, H2.2 and H2.3 are supported.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the previous analysis of the study hypotheses, it can be said that COSO ERM and Cyber risk management both seek to create a flexible and reliable cyber environment and enhance information and cyber security capabilities, Including human resources, technology and processes, to face the risks of information and cyber security, and to maintain the information at the bank within a secure environment through the various stages of its life cycle, starting from its creation, through its transmission, processing, storage, and ending with its destruction, including cooperate with the concerned authorities to build a participatory system to raise the level of readiness to respond to cybersecurity incidents, address information security and cybersecurity risks, and reduce the resulting effects to the acceptable level in the Bank. In addition to contributing to spreading and rooting awareness of information security and cybersecurity. As is the case in many studies, this study faced

many problems that we could find appropriate solutions to in the future, especially with regard to data collection. This study was limited to the results related to the banking sector in Jordan, and it may be possible to collect data from other sectors. The study also faced another problem, which is to focus on the Jordanian economy, which is considered one of the relatively weak types of economy, while future studies can deal with another type of The economy, which is represented in many developing countries, to search for economic and cultural effects in an extensive and larger way than what appeared in this study, and the study model can be tested in the light of those changes, in order to identify the suit...

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